

TRAKTORLARNI QISHLOQ HO'JALIGIDA ISHLATISHDA UNUMDORLIKNI HISOBGA OLISH

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Farg'ona viloyati Oltiariq tumani
2 son kasb hunar maktabi traktor va qishloq
xo'jalik agregatlari fani o'qituvchisi

Annotasiya: Maqolada qishloq xo'jaligida traktorlardan foydalanishda ularni xususiyatida kelib chiqib ishlatish, yer xosildorligini oshirishda traktorlardan foydalanishning ahamiyati va tuproqni texnogen ta'sirdan zichlanishini oldini olish masalalariga qisqacha to'xtalinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Tuproq, texnika, massa, qishloq xo'jaligi, zichlanish.

Аннотация: В статье кратко рассмотрено применение тракторов в сельском хозяйстве с учетом их характеристик, значение использования тракторов в повышении продуктивности земель, предотвращении уплотнения почвы вследствие техногенного воздействия.

Ключевые слова: Почва, техника, масса, земледелие, уплотнение.

Abstract: The article briefly discusses the use of tractors in agriculture, their use based on their characteristics, the importance of using tractors in increasing soil fertility, and the prevention of soil compaction from man-made influences.

Keywords: Soil, equipment, mass, agriculture, compaction

Keyingi yillarda qishloq xo'jaligi ishlab chiqarishida ish unumini oshirish uchun keng qamrovli, katta massaga ega bo'lgan g'ildirakli qishloq xo'jalik agregatlaridan foydalanish tobora ortib bormoqda. Bu esa ekin yetishtiriladigan dalalarning tuproqlari zichligini agregatlarning dalaga bir necha marta ishlov berish uchun kirishi natijasida g'ildiraklari ta'sirida tuproq zichlanishining keskin ortishiga olib kelmoqda. Shu bois, tuproqning texnogen ta'sirdan zichlanishini

oldini olish va uni kamaytirish yo'llarini izlash dolzarb muammolardan hisoblanadi. Paxta yetishtiriladigan xududlarning tuprog'i mexanik tarkibi bo'yicha og'ir, o'rta va yengil tuproqlarga bo'linadi. Paxtachilikda 65 foizdan ko'proq yer fondini og'ir tuproqqa kiruvchi och va tiniq kulrang bo'z tuproq tashkil etadi.

Markaziy Osiyoning sug'orib ekin ekiladigan yerlaridagi gumus miqdori va donadorliligi kam bo'lganligi sababli tuproqqa chopiq MTAlar bilan ishlov berilganda zichlanishga o'ta moyil bo'ladi. Tuproqning 0,5 m chuqurlikda yuzaga keladigan zichlanishi yoki qoldiq deformatsiyasi traktor yurish qismlarining o'lchami va ilashish xususiyatlari, dinamik yuklanish, massani tayanchlarga taqsimlanishi, ekinlarni yetishtirish texnologiyasi, tuproq unumdorligi va undagi organik birikmalarning mavjudligini hisobga olgan holda o'lchanadi.

Dalaga MTAlar bilan asosiy ishlov berilganda tuproq g'ovak holatda bo'ladi, ammo ekish oldi ishlovlarini o'tkazish va birinchi sug'orish natijasida u deyarli boshlang'ich zich holiga keladi. G'o'za yetishtirilib kelinayotgan tuproqlar zichlashishga moyil, chunki bu dalalarda haydalma qavat bilan haydov osti qatlami o'rtasida 6–8 sm qalinlikda zich qatlam paydo bo'ladi. Mana shu zich qatlam g'o'za ildizining rivojlanishiga to'sqinlik qiladi va tuproqdagi namlik, oziq elementlaridan foydalanishni cheklab qo'yadi. Natijada o'simlik ildizi qattiq qatlamga yetgandan so'ng tik o'sa olmay gorizontol yo'nalishda tarqaladi.

Zichlik 1,5–1,6 g/sm³ ni tashkil etganda chigit 3–5 kun kechikib unadi, buning ustiga nihollar nimjon, sarg'ish, ko'pincha ildiz chirish kasaliga duchor bo'ladi. Zichlikning maqbul me'yorlari quyidagicha:

1) qadimdan sug'orib kelinayotgan og'ir qumoqli va yengil soz tipik bo'z hamda o'tloqi, botqoq-o'tloqi tuproqlarda – 1,1-1,3 g/sm³ .

2) yangidan sug'orilayotgan o'rtacha qumoq yerlarda – 1,1-1,4 g/sm³ .

Sug'oriladigan tipik bo'z va gidromorf tuproqlarda zichlikning xatarli (kritik) chegarasi 1,5 g/sm³, yangidan sug'orilayotgan o'rtacha qumoq, och tusli bo'z tuproq va taqir tuproqlarda esa 1,6 g/sm³ ni tashkil etadi.

O.R. Kenjaevning Buxoro viloyatida olib borgan ilmiy tadqiqot ishlariga ko'ra, g'o'zaga ishlov berish davrida sug'oriladigan tuproqlarning mexanik tarkibi traktorlarni bir necha marta o'tib, ularni haddan tashqari (1,69–1,74 g/sm³ gacha) zichlab yuborilishi natijasida 20- 40 foizgacha yomonlashib, qattiqligi 2,8 dan 7,5 MPa gacha ortadi.

QXMEI tajriba uchastkasida olingan tadqiqot natijalarga ko'ra, ekishgacha tuproqning zichligi 1,22 g/sm³ ga, ekishdan keyin g'ildiraklar izida 1,62 g/sm³ ni tashkil etgan. Bunda zichlik me'yordan ortiqligini ko'rish mumkin.

Tuproq zichligining ortishi uning solishtirma qarshiligini 1,5-1,8 marotaba, unga ishlov berish xarajatlarini 20-30 foiz oshishiga va buning natijasida yonilg'ini 18 foizga ortiqcha sarflanishiga olib keladi.

Tuproq zichligining ortishi tufayli zanjirli traktor izlarida qattiqlik va tortishga qarshilik 25 foizga, g'ildirakli traktor izlarida foizga hamda yuk avtomobili va tirkamalar izlarida 65 foizgacha ortadi. Traktor izlaridagi tuproqning zichlanishi esa qishloq xo'jalik ekinlarining hosildorligini 5–40 foizga kamayishiga olib keladi.

Qatorlab yetishtiriladigan qishloq xo'jalik ekinlari uchun hosilni kamayishi nafaqat traktor izlarida, hattoki qo'shni qatorda ham kuzatilgan. Chopiq MTAlarining g'o'za qator oralariga birinchi va keyingi ishlov berishlar uchun bir necha marotaba kirishi g'ildiraklar ta'siridan tuproqning ortiqcha zichlanishi, har keyingi ishlov berishda qarshilikning ortishi natijasida qo'shimcha yonilg'i sarflanishi, ish organlarining yeyilishi va qo'shimcha xarajatlarning ortishi hamda bevosita ekin hosildorligining kamayishiga olib keladi. Shuning uchun shinaning tuproqqa zararli ta'sirining oldini olish hozirgi kunning dolzarb masalasi hisoblanadi.

Ammo traktorga tuproqyumshatgich o'rnatib, tuproqni yumshatish yangi texnologik jarayonni bajarishga olib keladi. Natijada, qo'shimcha yonilg'i va

mehnat sarfi talab etiladi. Ayniqsa, zamonaviy traktorlarning massasi katta bo'lib tuproqqa solishtirma bosimi ham unga mos ravishda katta bo'ladi.

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